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Characterization of steroid metabolism alterations induced by nutrient deprivation in human cells.

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We measured total transcription in human cells undergoing nutrient deprivation to understand how cancer cells mobilize steroid hormone biosynthesis during resistance to clinical interventions utilizing nutrient restriction (e.g., VEGF-A blockade, mTOR inhibition). We identified *DHRS3* activation as a major component of compensatory metabolic signaling in response to nutrient restriction in cancer cells.